

MICROSCOPIC AND MACROSCOPIC EVALUATION OF *DISTIMAKE* *QUINQUEFOLIUS* FOR PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STANDARDIZATION

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ABSTRACT

The pharmacognostic investigation of *Distimake quinquefolius* (L.) A.R. Simões & Staples aimed to establish a comprehensive standardization profile to support its authentic identification and quality control as a medicinal plant. The study integrated macroscopic, microscopic, histochemical, and quantitative evaluations following WHO guidelines. Macroscopic examination detailed the characteristic morphology of the plant, including its greenish lanceolate leaves, pale yellow to whitish funnel-shaped flowers, and bitter-tasting capsules. Microscopic and powder studies revealed distinctive diagnostic features like bicollateral vascular bundles, calcium oxalate crystals, tannin cells, trichomes, and spiral vessels, which are vital for detecting adulteration and confirming authenticity even in powdered form. Histochemical analyses confirmed the presence of major secondary metabolites such as lignin, mucilage, tannins, starch, fatty acids, and polyphenols, correlating with its ethnomedicinal uses for fever, arthritis, and skin disorders. Phytochemical references confirmed the occurrence of

alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, phytosterols, and cardiac glycosides, which collectively justify its traditional therapeutic applications. The pharmacognostic parameters standardized in this work provide a scientific foundation for the authentication, formulation, and quality assurance of *D. quinquefolius*-based herbal preparations, contributing to the broader pharmacopeial documentation and monographic data required for globally harmonized herbal regulation.

KEYWORDS: *Distimake quinquefolius*, pharmacognostic standardization, herbal medicine, microscopy, histochemical analysis.

INTRODUCTION^[1,2,4-14]

The most important things for consumers about medications are purity, safety, potency, and efficacy. Thereby, standardization and quality control of herbal medicines and raw material are always required. The popularity of the herbal drugs is increasing worldwide generally and particularly in the developed countries but one of the obstacles in its acceptability is lack of standard quality control profile. World Health Organization (WHO) emphasized including the physicochemical and the phytochemical evaluation of crude drug materials for developing standardized quality control profile of herbal medicine. Normally, most of the attention is paid to quality indices including macro- and microscopic examination, ash values, moisture content, extractive values, crude fiber, qualitative and quantitative chemical evaluation, and chromatographic examination.

Due to cultural and historic factors, popularity and dependency on medicinal plants have become a topic of global importance in both the developing and the developed world. Due to limited data of safety and efficacy, poor regulation, and control, the medicinal plants have now become a key issue in industrialized and developing countries. Both the general consumer and health-care professionals need up-to-date authoritative information on the safety and efficacy of medicinal plants. WHO encourages the countries to provide safe and effective traditional remedies and practices in public and private health services. Preparations of monographs are intended primarily to promote harmonization in the use of herbal medicines with respect to levels of safety, efficacy, and quality control.

Distimake quinquefolius L. A.R. Simões & Staples, a member of the Convolvulaceae family, is also recognized by several synonyms including *Ipomoea quinquefolia*, *Convolvulus quinquefolia*, and *Merremia quinquefolia*. Known by common names such as Five-Fingered

Morning Glory, Rock Rosemary, Snake Vine, Five-Leaf Distimake, and Five-Leaf Morning Glory, this species is found extensively across tropical and subtropical zones, spanning the Americas, the Bahamas, northern Brazil, India, and neighboring regions. Phytochemical studies reveal the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, phytosterols, fatty acids, and cardiac glycosides in the plant. In traditional medicine, it has been employed to address conditions like fever, headaches, skin diseases, joint inflammation, rheumatoid arthritis, scurvy, and digestive issues.^[3]

Pharmacognosy is the study of medicines derived from natural sources, mainly from plants. It basically deals with standardization, authentication and study of natural drugs. Most of the research in pharmacognosy has been done in identifying controversial species of plants, authentication of commonly used traditional medicinal plants through morphological, phytochemical and physicochemical analysis. The importance of pharmacognosy has been widely felt in recent times. Unlike taxonomic identification, pharmacognostic study includes parameters which help in identifying adulteration in dry powder form also. This is again necessary because once the plant is dried and made into powder form, it loses its morphological identity and easily prone to adulteration. Pharmacognostic studies ensure plant identity and lay down standardization parameters that help prevent adulterations. Such studies will help in authentication of the plants and ensures reproducible quality of herbal products which will lead to safety and efficacy of natural products. The pharmacognostic standardization parameters typically performed are described below.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Collection and Authentication

The whole plant of *Distimake quinquefolius* was collected from Veppampalayam village in Erode district, Tamil Nadu, India, and subsequently authenticated at the Botanical Survey of India, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore. A voucher specimen (No. BSI/SRC/5/23/2024-25/Tech/365) has been deposited in the herbarium for future reference.

Standardization parameters^[1,15]

Organoleptic characters: Organoleptic evaluation can be done by means of sense organs, which provide the simplest as well as quickest means to establish the identity and purity to ensure quality of a particular drug. Organoleptic characters such as shape, size, color, odor, taste and fracture of stem bark, leaf structure like margin, apex, base surface, venation and inflorescence, etc. are evaluated.

Macroscopic study: The macroscopic study is the morphological description of the plant parts which are seen by naked eye or magnifying lens.

Microscopic study: The microscopic study is the anatomical study which is done by taking appropriate section of the plant parts under study. Each distinguishing character can be noted down, some of which are retained in the powder study also. Some of the chemicals which are used in obtaining clear sections are phloroglucinol, chloral hydrate, safranin, methyl orange, etc.

Powder Microscopical study: Powder study is similar to microscopic study except here dried powder is taken instead of section of the plant. All the reagents used are also same like above.

Histochemical test analysis

Procedure

1. Add drops of the reagent to the sample and applying a cover-glass, then irrigate, using a strip of filter-paper as described below.
2. Place drops of the reagent on one edge of the cover-glass of a prepared specimen, place a strip of filter paper at the opposite edge of the cover-glass to remove the fluid under the cover-glass by section, causing the reagent to flow over the specimen.
3. Using the second method, the progress of the reaction may be observed under a microscope. Care should be taken to avoid using reagents or vapors that could attack the lenses or stages of the microscope.

1. **Lignified cell walls**-Moisten the powder or section on a slide with a small volume of phloroglucinol and allow to stand for about 2 minutes or until almost dry. Add 1 drop of Hydrochloric acid and apply a cover-glass; lignified cell walls are stained pink to cherry red.
2. **Suberized or cuticular cell walls** - Add 1-2 drops of Sudan red III and allow to stand for a few minutes or warm gently, Suberized or cuticular cell walls are stained orange red or red.
3. **Aleurone grains** - Add a few drops of iodine/ethanol, the aleurone grains will turn yellowish brown to brown.
4. **Calcium carbonate Crystals** or deposits of calcium carbonate dissolve slowly with effervescence when acetic acid or hydrochloric acid is added.

5. **Calcium oxalate Crystals** of calcium oxalate are insoluble in acetic acid but dissolve in hydrochloric acid without effervescence (if applied by irrigation the acid should be more concentrated); they also dissolve in sulphuric acid, but needle-shaped crystals of calcium sulphate separate on standing after about 10 minutes. In polarized light, calcium oxalate crystals are birefringent. Calcium oxalate is best viewed after clearing the sample, e.g., with chloral hydrate
6. **Fats, Fatty oils volatile oils and resins** - Add 1-2 drops of Sudan red III and allow to stand 7. for a few minutes or heat gently, if necessary. The fatty substances are staining orange-red to red. Irrigate the preparation with ethanol and heat gently, the volatile oil and resins dissolve in the solvent, while fats and fatty oils (except castor oil and croton oil) remain intact.
7. **Starch**-Add a small volume of iodine; a blue or reddish blue color is produced.
8. **Tannin**-Add 1 drop of ferric chloride; it turns bluish black of greenish black.
9. **Mucilage** - Add a few drops of ruthenium red; it turns red color.
10. **Polyphenols** - Add 1-2 drops of toluidine blue and allow to stand for a few minutes and then mount in glycerin; bluish green color is produced.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Macroscopical studies

The organoleptic characters including color, odor, taste and external features of *Distimake quinquefolius* were observed and the results were recorded in Table 1.

Table 1: Organoleptic characters of the *Distimake quinquefolius*.

Organoleptic Characters	Observations		
	LEAF	FLOWER	FRUIT
Colour	Greenish	Pale yellow to whitish	Green to brownish
Odor	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic
Taste	mild bitter	mild bitter	mild bitter
Size	2.5-6.5 cm long	1.8-2.5 cm long	7-10 mm in diameter
Shape	Five elliptic to lanceolate leaflets	Funnel or trumpet-shaped	Round or globular capsules

Microscopical studies

A. Transverse Section

1. Leaf

Fig. 1.1: Detailed TS of Midrib.

Fig. 1.2: Overview of Midrib.

Fig. 1.3: Lamina enlarged view.

Fig. 1.4: Midrib middle portion enlarged view.

UP-Upper Epidermis, GT-Granular trichomes, NGT-Non-Granular trichomes, LP-Lower Epidermis, BVB-Bicollateral vascular bundle, Sc- Secretary cells, X-Xylem, GP-Ground Parenchyma tissue, MR-Midrib, AdEp- Abaxial Epidermis, La-Lamina, PM-Palisade Mesophyll, SM- Spongy Mesophyll, S-Stomata, Scl- Sclerenchyma, MX-Metaxylem, PX-Primary xylem, Ph-Phloem.

2. Stem

Fig. 2.1: Detaild TS of stem.

Fig. 2.2: enlogred view of stem.

Fig. 2.3: enlogred view of stem pith.

GT- Granular trichomes, CCr-Cluster Crystals, P- Pith, IxP- Interxylary Phloem, T- Tannins, Sc-Secondary cortex, P-Parenchymatous pith, PX-Primary Xylem, SX- secondary Xylem, MX- Metaxylem, MRN- Medullary Ray-Narrow, LC- Lactiferous Cells, C- Cambium, SPh- Secondary Phloem, Ph-Phloem, BF-Bast Fibre, Ep- Epidermis, NGT- Non-Granular Trichomes, Pd- Periderm, X- Xylem.

3. Petiole

Fig. 3.1: Detailed TS of Petiole.

Fig. 3.2: enlarged view upper portion of petiole.

Fig. 3.3: enlarged view middle portion of petiole.

Ep- Epidermis, C- Cortex, Cc- Collenchyma cells, WB- Wing Bundle, P- Pith, X- Xylem, VB- Vascular Bundle, Ph- Phloem, GP- Ground Parenchyma Tissue, CCr- Calcium oxalate crystals, Ca- Cambium, PX-Primary Xylem.

4. Root

Fig. 4.1: Detailed TS of root bark.

Fig. 4.2: Detailed TS of root phloem.

Fig. 4.3: Detailed TS of root phloem and xylem.

Fig. 4.4: Detailed TS of root xylem.

Co- Cortex, CoCa- Cork Cambium, Sc- Suberized cells, SeC- Secretory Canal, Ph- Phloem, MR- Medullary Rays, SePh- Secondary Phloem, Ca- Cambium, SeX- Secondary Xylem, IxX- Intraxylary Xylem, X- Xylem, XV- Xylem Vessel, XF- Xylem Fibre.

5. Calyx

Fig. 5.1: Enlarged portion of mid Calyx.

Fig. 5.2: Enlarged view TS of calyx.

Fig. 5.3: Detailed TS of calyx.

Pd- Periderm, PM- Palisade Mesophyll, SM- Spongy Mesophyll, Ep- Epidermis, Cc- Collenchyma cells, GT- Granular Trichomes.

6. Testa

Fig. 6.1: Enlarged view of TS of Testa.

Fig. 6.2: overview of Testa.

Fig. 6.3: Detailed TS of Testa.

UEp- Upper Epidermis, T-Testa, ScF- Secondary Fibre, LEp- Lower Epidermis, Pd- Periderm

7. Seed

Fig. 7.1: Detailed TS of Cotyledon.

Fig. 7.2: Detailed TS of radicle.

Fig. 7.3: Detailed TS of Testa.

B. Powder Microscopic

1. Leaf

Fig. 8.1: Cluster crystals.

Fig. 8.2: Glandular trichomes.

Fig. 8.3: Lower Epidermis.

Fig. 8.4: Palisade cells.

Fig. 8.5: Petiole Epidermis.

Fig. 8.6: Sec. view of Epidermis.

Fig. 8.7: Spiral Vessels.

Fig. 8.8: Surface view of Epidermis.

2.Stem

Fig. 9.1: Cluster Crystals.

Fig. 9.2: Glandular Trichomes.

Fig. 10.3: Epidermis.

Fig. 10.4: Pitted Fibre.

Fig. 9.5: Spiral Vessels.

Fig. 9.6: Vascular Fragment.

3.Epicarp

Fig. 10.1: Epicarp cells.

Fig. 10.2: Oil globules.

Fig. 10.3: Scleroids.

Fig. 10.4: Stone Cells.

Fig. 10.5: Reticulate Vessels.

4. Seed

Fig. 11.8: Trichomes.

C. Histochemical Studies**Fig. 12.6: Phenol.**

D. Quantitative Microscopy

1. Stomata

Fig. 13.1: Lower Epidermis – Paracytic Stomata.

Fig. 13.2: Upper Epidermis – Paracytic Stomata.

2. Vein islet

Fig. 14: Upper epidermis – Vein Islet.

DISCUSSION

The pharmacognostical evaluation of *Distimake quinquefolius* establishes a comprehensive standardization profile essential for its authentication and quality control as an herbal medicine. The study detailed its macroscopic, microscopic, and histochemical characteristics, confirming the plant's diagnostic features such as bicollateral vascular bundles, granular and non-granular trichomes, calcium oxalate crystals, tannins, and glandular structures across various tissues including leaf, stem, root, and seed. Macroscopic examination showed greenish leaves, pale yellow to whitish funnel-shaped flowers, and round brownish fruits with a mild bitter taste. Microscopic and powder analyses revealed structural components like spiral vessels, reticulate Scleroids, and secretory cells that authenticate the plant in powdered form, preventing adulteration. Histochemical assays identified key secondary metabolites such as lignin, starch, tannins, mucilage, and polyphenols, correlating with its traditional

therapeutic use for fever, pain, skin disorders, and inflammation. Phytochemical diversity, including alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, phytosterols, and cardiac glycosides, emphasizes its pharmacological potential within the Convolvulaceae family, comparable to genera like *Ipomoea* and *Merremia*. These comprehensive findings, consistent with WHO-standardized procedures, confirm that *D. quinquefolius* is a taxonomically valid and pharmacognostically distinct species rich in bioactive compounds, making it a valuable candidate for future phytochemical, pharmacological, and formulation research aimed at validating its ethnomedicinal claims and ensuring the reproducible quality and safety of its herbal preparations.

CONCLUSION

The study conclusively establishes *Distimake quinquefolius* as a pharmacognostically distinct and phytochemically rich species within Convolvulaceae, exhibiting anatomical, histological, and chemical traits consistent with other bioactive genera like *Ipomoea* and *Merremia*. The comprehensive evaluation of its organoleptic, microscopic, and histochemical characteristics presents reliable diagnostic markers that ensure its proper identification and prevent adulteration in herbal markets. The detection of diverse bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and polyphenols, affirms its therapeutic potential and supports its traditional use against inflammatory, rheumatic, and cutaneous ailments. Overall, these results form a scientific baseline for future phytochemical isolation, pharmacological evaluation, and standard formulation development, reinforcing the medicinal significance of *D. quinquefolius* while fulfilling the WHO's criteria for herbal drug standardization and global pharmacognostic validation.

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